

**A Comparison between the Platonic, Neo-Platonic, Manichean, and Augustine's Approach
to the Problem of Evil**

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Introduction

The problem of evil perplexes not just the philosophical world but also the world in general. Even the earliest philosophers confronted this issue and sought an answer. According to Lactantius, Epicurus famously said with regard to the problem of evil:

God,..., either wishes to take away evils, and is unable; or He is able, and is unwilling; or He is neither willing nor able, or He is both willing and able. If He is willing and is unable, He is feeble, which is not in accordance with the character of God; if He is able and unwilling, He is envious, which is equally at variance with God; if He is neither willing nor able, He is both envious and feeble, and therefore not God; if He is both willing and able, which alone is suitable to God, from what source then are evils? Or why does He not remove them?¹

Attempts to answer to this question usually fall into three broad categories: evil does not exist, and it is only subjective perception that makes something good or bad; evil does exist, but God is not the cause of it (this approach can lead to a dualistic approach of having two gods); or evil exists and God is the cause of it. First this paper, will discuss the viewpoints of three pre-Augustinian philosophical traditions, namely, Platonic (Plato), Neo Platonic (Plotinus), and Manichean. These will provide us a background to Augustine's philosophy. Next, the paper will show how Augustine baptizes the philosophy of his predecessors and enriches the Christian heritage with Greco-Roman heritage.

Plato

Plato was the student of Socrates and one of the fathers of classical philosophy. He lived during the 5th and 4th century B.C.E. He was born in Athens, Greece, and was the founder of the first philosophical school in the western world, called the Academy. It is quite difficult for one to

¹ Lactantius, *A Treatise on the Anger of God*, trans. by William Fletcher, eds. by Alexander Roberts and James Donaldson, Ante Nicene Fathers Volume VII, American Edition, (New York, NY: The Christian Literature Company, 1890), XIII, 271.

distinguish between Socrates' thought and Plato's thought. Plato wrote all of his works in the form of dialogues. This approach while easy and entertaining to read, conceals more than it reveals. Most of his works describe what a virtue or thing is *not* but fail to define what it *is*. Thus, to understand Plato's theodicy we must dive into several of his works, a central theme of which is the doctrine of the Forms, which he uses to provide a realistic solution to the problem of universals.

Plato held the stance that God could not be the source of evil, but only of good.² Plato mostly deals with the aspect of moral evil in his works. Though regarding natural evil in *The Republic*, he does state that the evil which man faces is the necessary result of some previous wrongdoing.³ To understand Plato's answer to the problem of evil, we must first understand Plato's anthropology and metaphysics. In the *Phaedrus*, Plato shares the allegory of the chariot to explain the tripartite nature of the human soul. The three parts of the soul are the Reason, the Spirit, and the Appetites. The Spirit for Plato is described as an immortal winged horse who is "a lover of honor with modesty and self-control; companion of true glory, he needs no whip, and is guided by verbal commands alone." The Appetites are described by Plato as a mortal winged horse who is a "companion to wild boasts and indecency, he is shaggy around the ears-deaf as a post-and just barely yields to horsewhip and goad combined."⁴ The Reason for Plato is described as the charioteer who directs the horses so that he may behold the Forms: essences of things like Beauty, Wisdom, Courage, Justice, and Goodness. Thus, according to Plato, the Appetites and

² Plato, *Plato's Republic*, trans. G.M.A. Grube (Indianapolis, IN: Hackett Publishing Company, 1988), Book II, 379c, p. 49.

³ *Ibid.*, Book X, 613a, p. 256.

⁴ Plato, *Phaedrus*, trans. Alexander Nehamas and Paul Woodruff (Indianapolis, IN: Hackett Publishing Company, 1995), 253d-e, p. 44.

Spirit are the lower part of the soul, while, the Reason is the higher part of the soul. As Plato identified virtue with the knowledge of the Forms, evil therefore came from the lack of knowledge. Thus, according to Plato, if the charioteer has a lack of knowledge of the true good, the bad horse can overpower him and drive him in another direction.

In the *Republic*, Plato discusses the nature and definition of justice. In order to explain this, Plato shifts his focus from the individual to society. He asserts that what is good or evil in the external order of society depends upon the inner nature of the soul and that whatever is true for society is also true for the individual. In Books V to VII, Plato describes his notion of the Philosopher king. He asserts that the perfect human life would be that which is governed by knowledge. The cause of all evil is because men are seduced by their own passions. This leads to the corruption of man's desire to attain the truth.⁵ Furthermore, in the *Protagoras*, Plato states that a person who has knowledge isn't swayed by his passions and desires; rather, he is governed by knowledge. Thus, whoever learns to differentiate between good and bad will never be swayed. Plato believes that intelligence is sufficient and necessary for mankind to be happy and not commit evil deeds.⁶

In the *Meno*, during Meno and Socrates' discussion of the definition of virtue, the question regarding whether people can knowingly do evil comes up. To which Socrates replies, "It is clear then that those who do not know things to be bad do not desire what is bad, but they

⁵ Richard Lewis Nettleship, *Lectures on the Republic of Plato*, Second Edition, ed. Lord Charnwood (London: Macmillan and Co., 1922), 12.

⁶ Plato, *Protagoras*, trans. Stanley Lombardo and Karen Bell (Indianapolis, IN: Hackett Publishing Company, 1992), 352c, p. 49.

desire those things that they believe to be good but that are in fact bad. It follows that those who have no knowledge of these things and believe them to be good clearly desire good things.”⁷

The above passages demonstrate that for Plato, “when a man chooses that which is *de facto* evil, he chooses it *sub specie boni*: he desires something which he imagines to be good, but which is, as a matter of fact, evil.”⁸ Thus, according to Plato, moral evil is a result of ignorance—more specifically, ignorance of the Forms. Therefore, if a person is aware and is knowledgeable with regards to the Forms, he will not commit evil, and thus there will not be any evil.

Plotinus

Plotinus was born in Lycopolis, Egypt, in the 3rd Century A.D. He was a student of Ammonius Saccas. Most of what we know about him comes from the *Enneads*, which are edited and compiled by his student Porphyry. Plotinus was a Platonist but also had knowledge of Aristotle. His main desire was to create a system for Platonic Philosophy. In this process he also included Aristotelian philosophy in the places where Plato did not adequately provide an answer or for the points which he did not address. Thus this amalgamation ended up forming a new philosophical system which would later be known as Neo-Platonism.

As a follower of Plato, Plotinus also believed that the One, i.e., the Good, was not capable of evil. To understand Plotinus’ view on evil, we must understand his metaphysics. According to Plotinus, the whole universe is an emanation of the One. For Plotinus, there are three hypotheses: the One, the *Nous*, and the Universal Soul. He argues that we cannot really

⁷ Plato, *Meno*, trans. G.M.A. Grube (Indianapolis, IN: Hackett Publishing Company, 1976), 77d-e, p. 10.

⁸ Frederick Copleston, *A History of Philosophy*, Book One, Vol. 1, *Greece to Rome* (New York, NY: Image Books, 1985), 219.

understand what the One is, since any description might only be an attribute.⁹ Plotinus like Plato, also does claim that the One is good and beyond the grasp of the intellect.¹⁰ “The ‘One’ ‘willing itself’ is its own revelation. This ‘will to itself’ ‘ever producing itself’ is the *Nous*, ‘ever productive thinking’ of an ‘ever productive thing’, the latter being the ideas.”¹¹ The *Nous* is the place where Plotinus deposited the Forms of Plato. But these ideas alone cannot cause motion. Thus, borrowing from Thales, the idea that the soul is the principle of motion, he established that there is a Universal Soul. This Universal Soul receives ideas *Eikons* (primordial image) from the *Nous* and imprints them on unformed void matter.¹² Thus, the Universal Soul becomes a kind of mediator between the *Nous* and matter. It looks upwards to the *Nous*, contemplating the eternal ideas, and then gives life to nature via emanation. The human soul is an emanation of the Universal Soul. The human soul is like the Universal, as it too shares in the *Nous* and matter, i.e., body.

Matter (*hule*), according to Plotinus, is the last step in the ladder.¹³ Plotinus compares the emanation to a light whose source is the One. This light gets dimmer as it goes further away from the One, and thus by the time it reaches matter, it becomes total darkness, i.e., privation of the One. Plotinus seems to draw on the Aristotelian concept of prime matter here to explain matter. To understand Plotinus’ view of matter, we can consider an object or a body and if we

⁹ Plotinus, *The Enneads*, 4th ed., trans. Stephen Mackenna, rev. B. S. Page (New York: Pantheon Books, 1969), Book VI, 8, 11, p. 604-605.

¹⁰ *Ibid.*, Book VI, 7, 37, p. 590-591.

¹¹ Eugen Kullmann, “Alexandrian Philosophy,” in *A History of Philosophical Systems*, ed. Vergilius Ferm (New York: The Philosophical Library, 1950), 137.

¹² *Ibid.*, 138.

¹³ *Ibid.*, Book I, 8, 7, p. 245.

completely abstract the form from it, then the residuum is what matter is.¹⁴ Matter in Plotinus' view is not evil, but it is the principle of evil. In so far as matter is in contact with the Universal Soul, it is not complete darkness.

In the *Enneads*, Plotinus states, "To begin with, the soul is neither independent of matter, nor by herself, perverse. By virtue of her union with the body, which is material, she is mingled with indetermination, and so to a certain point, deprived of the form which embellishes and which supplies measure."¹⁵ Thus, for Plotinus the root of moral evil is that though the soul is rational and desires to contemplate the One, it is attached to a body which can become an obstacle. The body by its nature is not evil. However, since it impedes the return of the human soul back to the One, it becomes a sort of metaphysical evil. For a human soul which is in contact with its prior through contemplation, governing matter becomes an effortless task. But when the soul becomes forgetful and stops contemplating its prior, becoming devoid of light of the One, it begins to be swayed by matter. Thus, the soul begins to take pleasure in matter; after a while, it becomes governed by it. This becomes the source of unhappiness, hatred, and evil.¹⁶ Thus, in this state the human soul does not desire to free from the body and return back home, i.e., to the One, but desires to stay. In this way, a human soul's moral struggle occurs between the souls desire to return to the One and his desire to take pleasure in matter and thus be controlled by it. Evil, according to Plotinus, is the absence of order.

¹⁴ Frederick Copleston, *A History of Philosophy*, 469.

¹⁵ Plotinus, *Plotinus Complete Works*, Volume 4, trans. Kenneth Sylvan Guthrie (Alpine, NJ: Comparative Literature Press, 1918), Book I, 8, 4, p. 1147.

¹⁶ Edward Moore, "Plotinus", *Internet Encyclopedia of Philosophy*, accessed April 3, 2019, <https://www.iep.utm.edu/plotinus>.

Manichean

Manichaeism is a religion founded by the Iranian prophet Mani. Mani lived in the 3rd century C.E. Manichaeism is a rigid, dualistic Gnostic religion. The religion gained a lot of popularity in the ancient world and spread to various places such as Persia, North Africa, China, Rome, and India. Mani claimed to be the last prophet and the *Paraclete* which Jesus had promised. The Manichean church had two classes: the elects (*electi*) and auditors (*auditores*). Only the elects needed to follow the strict disciplines prescribed by Mani.¹⁷

To understand the Manichean concept of the problem of evil, we must first understand its ontological dualistic conception of the structure of the world. Mani, in the *Fundamental Epistle* clearly states, “In the primeval beginning there were the two substances separated from one another.”¹⁸ The two substances were co-eternal and coexisting, always in conflict with each other. The Good refers to the Kingdom of Light from where knowledge, heaven, and the soul come. Evil refers to the Kingdom of Darkness, from where ignorance, matter, and the body come. According to the Manichean account, the forces of Evil invaded the Good and during this attempt, there was a mixture of good and bad. Therefore, the Good is always in an eternal battle to free itself from the Evil that surrounds it.

The world, according to the Manicheans, was created by the Evil so that they could trap the Good within it. Thus, a human being is a soul (good) trapped in a body (evil), and thus there is a constant battle between the body and the soul. In the *Acta Archelai*, the Manichean concludes his speech on anthropology by stating that the “body does not belong to God, but to

¹⁷ Augustine, *The De Haeresibus of Saint Augustine*, trans. Liguori G. Muller (Washington, DC: Catholic University of America Press, 1956), 87.

¹⁸ Mani, *The Fundamental Epistle*, eds. Iain Gardner and Samuel N. C. Lieu, Manichean text from the Roman Empire (Cambridge: The Press Syndicate of the University of Cambridge, 2004), 169.

matter, that it is dark and must be kept in the dark.”¹⁹ St. Augustine, when speaking about the Manichean conception of the world, states “Then they [the Manicheans] declare that the world has been made by the nature of the good, that is, by the nature of God, but yet that it was formed of a mixture of good and evil which resulted when these two natures fought among themselves.”²⁰

Thus, Evil according to the Manicheans is not a privation or lack of something but an active agent. Every physical evil is a result or has a one-to-one correspondence with the metaphysical evil. This accordingly explains the internal spiritual evil suffered by a person. One of the distinct advantages of this view is that a follower can always blame the cosmic maelstrom for his failures and in this way avoid personal blame.

Augustine

Augustine lived during 354 A.D.-430 A.D. He was born in Thagaste, Numidia. He was a rhetorician by profession. He first fell in love with philosophy after readings Cicero’s *Hortensius*. He would later become the Bishop of Hippo and one of the Church Fathers and Doctors whose writings would be a landmark for the ages to come. Augustine’s understanding of evil is very unique as he is well versed with the above three views of evil. He was a Manichean for about a decade as an *auditor*, but he then became a skeptic after leaving the Manichean religion. Later on, he was introduced to Plotinus by Ambrose. He uses quite a bit of Plotinus for his view on evil but does make a couple of distinctions. Throughout his many works he continuously criticizes the strong Manichean dualism, stating that it is illogical and a false approach to religion. As a Christian, Augustine had to reconcile how there could be a good God

¹⁹ Hegemonius, *Acta Archelai*, eds. Iain Gardner and Samuel N. C. Lieu, Manichean text from the Roman Empire (Cambridge: The Press Syndicate of the University of Cambridge, 2004), 185.

²⁰ Augustine, *The De Haeresibus of Saint Augustine*, 87.

while evil is present in the world. He also believed in the doctrine of creation *ex nihilo* and that everything came from God; thus, if evil were a thing, then it would find its origin in God.

Therefore, God would not be good.

Augustine rejects and condemns the Manichean position time and again. One thing which troubled Augustine was how matter, being evil, produced such beautiful and good things. He rejects the Manichean position frequently in the *Enchiridion*. He states that it is impossible for anything to have two disjunctive and opposite characteristics at the same time. For example, he states “No weather is both dark and bright at the same time; no food or drink is both sweet and sour at the same time; nobody is, at the same time and place, both white and black, nor deformed and well formed at the same time.”²¹ He then states that evil cannot exist without good, but there can be good without evil. Thus, he concludes that if there is no good then there can be no evil. In this sense, Augustine incorporates into his philosophy the Neo Platonic notion of privation, by stating that evil is not a thing by itself but a privation of the good. In *Concerning the Nature of Good against the Manichean*, he further states,

When accordingly it is inquired, whence is evil, it must first be inquired, what is evil, which is nothing else than corruption, either of the measure, or the form, or the order, that belong to nature. Nature therefore which has been corrupted, is called evil, for assuredly when incorrupt it is good; but even when corrupt, so far as it is nature it is good, so far as it is corrupted it is evil.²²

Here he goes farther than Plotinus, stating that evil is not merely a privation of the good but a corruption of it. Although God created everything to be good and beautiful, this does not stop it

²¹ Augustine, *Enchiridion*, ed. and trans. by Albert Cook Outler, Augustine: Confessions and Enchiridion (Louisville, KY: Westminster John Knox Press, 2006), 345.

²² Augustine, *Concerning the Nature of Good against the Manichean*, trans. Dr. Newman, ed. Philip Schaff, A Select Library of Nicene and Post-Nicene Fathers of the Christian Church Volume 4 (New York, NY: Charles Scribner's Sons, 1885), 352.

from being misused or corrupted. However, Augustine does note that nothing is completely evil; if it were so, it would cease to exist.²³

While Augustine does accept Plato's and Plotinus' views on certain topics, he nevertheless finds issues with them. With regards to Plato, he is unable to reconcile how the as a lower part of the soul, the Appetites can drive the Reason which is the higher part of the soul. While he does accept the Plotinus' theory of privation, he rejects the theory of emanation and the idea that matter is a principle of evil. For Augustine, matter is good in all aspects as it was created by God, the supreme Good.²⁴ From Augustine's writings one can oftentimes see influences of Stoicism. Augustine's combines the Neo-Platonic view of moral order as a hierarchy in which eternal things are of the highest value with the Stoic view that everyone and everything in the universe is part of the natural order and governed by the laws of nature, though our minds have the power to judge and order our desires.²⁵ He then "Christianizes" these views to help him develop his doctrine of the problem of evil.

To understand Augustine's view on evil, we must first understand his concept of the tripartite mind. In *On Free Choice of the Will*, Augustine introduces us to the concept of the Will or *Voluntas*. While struggling with the question of how desires (or Appetites), which is a lower and weaker part of the soul can drive the Intellect (or Reason), which is the higher part, thus causing a man to fall, Augustine introduced the tripartite model of the mind, i.e., the Memory, Intellect, and Will, which are all ontologically equal. For Augustine it is the Will which allows

²³ Augustine, *Confessions*, ed. and trans. by Albert Cook Outler, Augustine: Confessions and Enchiridion (Louisville, KY: Westminster John Knox Press, 2006), Book VII, 148.

²⁴ Augustine, *On True Religion*, ed. John H. S. Burleigh, Augustine: Earlier Writings (Louisville, KY: Westminster John Knox Press, 2006), 236.

²⁵ Marcia L. Colish, *Medieval Foundations of the Western Intellectual Tradition 400-2400* (London: Yale University Press, 1997), 28.

man to choose to do the bad, and thus a lower power does not conquer a higher power; rather a higher power chooses a lower. That being said, Augustine also believes that the Will has been corrupted due to Original Sin, thereby leaving people inclined to choose evil. While he maintained that the cross and resurrection of Christ frees us from Original sin, we can only completely gain an uncorrupted will by accepting the salvation of Christ.

Evil for Augustine is a privation of something (a good) that ought to be. For example, blindness is the privation of sight. What ought to be there is defined by nature, which is the standard. Thus, a horse not being able to fly is a privation but not an evil, as it is not in the nature of the horse to fly. Augustine divides evil into two categories: Natural Evil/ *Malum Poenae* (the evil that we suffer) and Moral Evil/ *Malum Culpa*e (the evil that we do).²⁶

Natural Evil/ *Malum Poenae* is defined as a privation in nature. Augustine associates physical evil, which humans face, such as the lack of sight or a limb, to the sin of Adam and Eve, i.e., Original Sin. Original Sin brought about a break in the natural order of things and thus a curse on man. Original sin is the root of all evil. In addressing the evils such as earthquakes, plagues, and volcanic eruptions, “Augustine calls on of Stoic theodicy, along the lines of Lactantius’ *First Apology*.”²⁷ He states that when we look at the larger scale of things, those events are not evil. As good always replaces evil in the long run, the events are always good. For example, a volcanic eruption in the short run might ruin farm land, but over time it would increase the soil’s fertility. Thus, evil in this case is not really an evil but the lack of adjustment of one’s attitude.

²⁶ Augustine, *On Free Choice of the Will*, trans. Thomas Williams (Indianapolis, IN: Hackett Publishing Company, 1993), Book I, 1.

²⁷ Colish, *Medieval Foundations of the Western Intellectual Tradition 400-2400*, 31.

When it comes to Moral Evil/*Malum Culpae*, Augustine defines moral evil as a privation in one's will. In *On True Religion*, Augustine provides a discourse regarding the source of moral evil is. While free will is its ultimate cause, for Augustine, substantial evil does not exist. Thus, Augustine seems to draw on Platonic philosophy stating that a person does not choose a supreme evil over a supreme good but instead chooses a temporal good instead of "an eternal one or a carnal one instead of a spiritual, or a sensible one to intelligible."²⁸ In this way, a person commits evil by choosing a lower good instead of a higher. For Augustine no substance is evil as everything comes from God, but preferring to love something of the lower order rather than the higher order is what leads to sin and hence, Moral Evil and punishment. Augustine offers a beautiful example of this. He states that water by itself is not evil, but if a person throws himself into it and drowns, the act of doing so is evil.²⁹ For Augustine a voluntary free act contain the elements of measure, form, and order. If they are not present in the perfect amount in any determined act, then, that act is considered imperfect and therefore, evil.³⁰

Conclusion

The way in which the answer to the problem of evil has evolved throughout the age of philosophy gives us a unique insight into how philosophy grows and develops over time. Augustine's reconciliation of faith and reason using the knowledge of the ancients is like Israel's plundering of gold from Egypt.³¹ Augustine baptizes Platonic, Neo Platonic, and Stoic

²⁸ Augustine, *On True Religion*, 243.

²⁹ Ibid.

³⁰ Etienne Gilson, *The Christian Philosophy of Saint Augustine*, trans. L. E. M. Lynch (New York: Vintage Books, 1967), 144.

³¹ Augustine, *On Christian Doctrine*, trans. D.W. Robertson, JR. (Upper Saddle River, NJ: Prentice Hall, 1958), Book II, 75.

philosophies and incorporates them into the Christian faith. Augustine's understanding of free will distinguishes his approach to the problem of evil from that of his predecessors because it places complete culpability on the individual. Augustine's theodicy differs from Platonism, which asserts that a person can be excused because of lack of knowledge, and from Manichaeism, which views the person as engaging in a battle between good and evil; and from Neo-Platonism, where in the notion of evil is quite ambiguous. Augustine's notion of free choice of the will shifts the blame onto the human being. While maintaining the goodness of God and the objects he created. Augustine also in some ways breaks away from the dualistic views of his predecessors and thus forms a theodicy which is compatible with the Christian view of God. Because Augustine does not fully resolve the issue, the topic continues to be debated and discussed. Augustine stands out as one of the first Christian philosophers to approach this topic in such an extensive and logical way.

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